

(iii) The complexes 3 and 7 contain urea which is capable of coordinating through nitrogen or oxygen. In both the complexes a broad band appears at 3320 cm^{-1} (N—H stretching) and its broadening is due to its coupling with the corresponding band of ammonia. The carbonyl stretching frequency is observed at 1660 cm^{-1} and its negative shift corresponds to the coordination of urea through oxygen. The complexes 4 and 8 contain thiourea as ligand and in their spectra two distinct bands appear at 1500 and 730 cm^{-1} assigned to C—N and C—S stretches. The increase in the former and decrease in the later support the coordination of thiourea through sulphur^{7,8}.

As copper(I) and silver(I) ions belong to d^{10} or spin-paired configurations, the magnetic moment values of the complexes are expected to correspond only to chromium(III) ion with three unpaired electrons and thus fall around 3.89 B.M. The electronic spectra also shows bands at 25 00, 19.00 and 13.50 kK characteristic of octahedrally coordinated chromium (III), as no d-d bands are possible theoretically for the above metal(I) ions.

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Organophosphonic Acids as Complexones. Part-VI. Reactions of Hydroxyethylidenediphosphonic Acid with Bivalent Metal Ions

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IN continuation to our work on metal derivatives of organophosphonic acids¹, we report here the synthesis and structural studies of metal derivatives of hydroxyethylidenediphosphonic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio. In the present investigation, reactions

with bivalent metals, Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} have been carried out.

Experimental

Phosphorus trichloride and glacial acetic acid (B.D.H.) and bivalent metal acetates (B.D.H., AnalaR) were used as such.

Preparation of ligand: The ligand, HEDP, was prepared as reported earlier¹ and was also obtained as an aqueous solution from M/s Aquapharm (India) as a gift.

Preparation of metal derivatives: Aqueous solution of the acid (1 mol) was added to metal salt solution (1 mol) with constant stirring at room temperature. The precipitation was effected by dropwise addition of acetone. The precipitates were filtered and washed with distilled water containing acetone and then dried at $70\text{--}80^\circ$ till constant weight. The compounds were neither soluble in water nor in any other common organic solvents. These compounds also did not melt when heated even upto 270° . Elemental analyses data, using conventional methods, and colour of the compounds have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL STATE, ELEMENTAL ANALYSES
AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compound	Colour and State	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	P	
MnHEDP.H ₂ O	White solid	19.93 (19.83)	22.28 (22.38)	5.67
Co HEDP.2H ₂ O	Pink solid	19.38 (19.71)	21.06 (20.73)	5.6
Ni HEDP.2H ₂ O	Green solid	19.94 (19.65)	19.91 (20.75)	3.3
Cu HEDP.2H ₂ O	Blue solid	21.29 (20.94)	20.34 (20.42)	2.02
Zn HEDP.2H ₂ O	White solid	20.97 (21.40)	20.10 (20.30)	—
Cd HEDP.2H ₂ O	White solid	31.94 (31.89)	17.39 (17.59)	—

IR spectra (nujol, KBr) were taken on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra were run on an Unicam SP-700 spectrophotometer with a standard reflectance accessory, using MgO as the reference. Magnetic measurements were made on Gouy balance.

Thermal analysis of the compounds were done in the atmosphere of air at National Chemical Laboratory, Pune. The specimens were heated at the rate of 10° min^{-1} in $20\text{--}1000^\circ$ range, and heated alumina was used as the standard.

Results and Discussion

Different bands of the free ligand and its complexes in their infrared spectra have been given in Table 2. Phosphoryl frequency ($1170\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the free ligand is lowered on coordination of the phosphoryl oxygen to the metal atoms of either the same or other molecules². δ_{OOR} mode (1035 cm^{-1}) of the free ligand HEDP is displaced to higher

frequency and is presumably due to coordination of hydroxyl oxygen to the metal atoms without any loss of hydrogen³. A single 930 cm⁻¹ band in free HEDP due to $\nu_s(\text{PO}_3)$ splits into two components at 930 and 950 cm⁻¹ on complex formation, suggesting the presence of two types of PO_3 groups. The 995 cm⁻¹ band in the complexes is due to coordinated phosphonic group. Antisymmetric vibrational bands $\nu_{as}(\text{PO}_3)$ are observed in the 1100-1150 cm⁻¹ region. A band at 440-400 cm⁻¹ region in the far-infrared spectra of copper(II)-, nickel(II)- and cobalt(II)-HEDP complexes (Table 2) was assigned to ν_{M-O} vibrations⁴.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA FOR FREE LIGAND AND ITS DIFFERENT BIVALENT METAL DERIVATIVES

Assignments	HEDP	Mn ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺
δ_{COH}	1035	1050	1050	1050	1055	1050	1050
$\nu_{P=O}$	1170 br 1204 br	1150	1150	1155	1150	1150	1150
$\nu_{sym} \text{PO}_3$	930	990 920	985 945	950 br	995 930	950 920	950 930
$\nu_{asym} \text{PO}_3$	1020	1090	1120	1100	1150	1090	1100
ν_{-OH_2}	3500	3440	3430	3400	3400	3370	3440
δ_{OH_2}	—	1625	1630	1650	1630	1630	1630
ν_{M-O}	—	—	440	440	400	—	—

br = Broad.

Thermal analysis: Since the general scheme of thermal decomposition is the same for all complexonates, only the derivatogram of cobalt(II) salt has, therefore, been given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Derivatogram of CoHEDP.2H₂O (100 mg specimen).

The thermogravimetric curve for cobalt(II) salt shows that it is stable at room temperature. There

is continuous mass loss of 18% (theoretically 18.06%) upto 180° and this corresponds to loss of three molecules of water. It is accompanied by endothermic effect with the minima at 150°. Out of these three water molecules, two are water of crystallisation and the third is lost perhaps from the ligand itself. The second mass loss of 9% takes place between 240 and 335° and is endothermic in nature having the minima at 280° and an inflection at 335°. Thus total mass loss is 27% (theoretical 27.7%) which indicates that the final product of thermal decomposition is CoO.P₂O₅.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra: Magnetic moment of cobalt, nickel, copper and manganese complexes have been found to be 5.6, 3.3, 2.02 and 5.67 B.M., and are within the ranges required for spin-free d⁷, d⁸, d⁹ and d⁵ systems, respectively. In case of cobalt complex magnetic moment is almost temperature independent. These values suggest the complexes to be octahedral and that the metal ions are well separated having no spin-spin interaction.

Electronic spectral data permit an unambiguous structural assignments. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of cobalt(II) complex shows a broad band at 8500 cm⁻¹ and another at 19420 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴T_{2g}(F) ← ⁴T_{1g} and ⁴T_{1g}(P) ← ⁴T_{1g} transitions, respectively and are in agreement with octahedral configuration. Similar suggestions were also made by Dunn as well as Lever⁵. A shoulder at 21050 cm⁻¹ on the principal band may be due either to lower symmetry component of ligand field or to the presence of spin-forbidden transitions⁵. In the case of nickel(II) complex spectrum, three bands at 8230, 13517 and 25970 cm⁻¹ were observed arising from the transition for ³A_{2g} ground state to excited levels ³T_{2g}(F), ³T_{1g}(F) and ³T_{1g}(P), respectively. Electronic spectrum of copper(II) complex showed one transition at 13330 cm⁻¹ due to distortion in octahedral symmetry⁶. Another band at 16310 cm⁻¹ was also observed.

ZnL.2H₂O and CdL.2H₂O: As expected for d¹⁰ system these are diamagnetic in nature.

In view of the studies made so far and also from the properties of the compounds, like their insolubility in different common organic solvents and their very high melting points (> 270°), a general polymeric octahedral structure for the compounds is indicated.

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Role of π -interaction in Ternary Complexes of Zinc(II) or Cadmium(II) + 2,2'-Bipyridyl + Amino Acids

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MIXED ligand complexes MAL, where M = Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺; A = 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline; and L = amino acids, have been studied earlier¹. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to determine the stability constants of the title systems using modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration technique. The [M(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺, 1:1 complex formed before pH ~ 4 and stable up to pH ~ 8 where the secondary ligand gets coordinated. Formation of 1:1 complexes of both [Ni(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ and [Zn(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ at low pH and their stability at high pH has been shown earlier^{2,4}.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. quality. Metal perchlorates were used in the present study to avoid the complexing tendency of the anion.

The experimental set-up and calculations described by Bhattacharya *et al.*⁵ were employed. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M in each case. Systronics 355 digital pH meter was employed for pH measurements. Potentiometric titrations were carried out at 30° using 0.2M NaOH.

The interpretation of the potentiometric curves was similar to that reported¹. From the titration data \bar{n}_H , \bar{n} and P_Z were calculated as described earlier⁵. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{MA} were determined by the method of averages⁶ and the values are presented in the Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The order of the formation constants of the mixed ligand chelates is the same as that for the binary complexes. It is observed that the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} are nearly equal to K_{ML}^M . This can be explained in terms of secondary ligands basicities. The order of mixed ligand formation constant is, glycine \approx α -alanine \approx leucine; valine \approx serine \approx threonine \approx methionine.

The higher values of mixed ligand formation constants can be explained by the special behaviour of 2,2'-bipyridyl. The 2,2'-bipyridyl molecule is bound to the metal ion by σ -bonding. Besides that there is also π -bonding formation by the back donation of electrons from M \rightarrow L. The $d\pi-p\pi$ interaction has been observed by earlier workers⁷. The positive charge on the metal ion in [M(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ and [M(aq)]²⁺ complexes is same, because the $d\pi-p\pi$ interaction does not allow the concentration of electrons on the metal ion to increase significantly. Therefore, the electronegativity of the metal ion in [M(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ remains same as in [M(aq)]²⁺. So, the tendency of the secondary ligand L to combine with [M(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ and [M(aq)]²⁺ is comparable. Therefore, K_{MAL}^{MA} values are nearly equal to K_{ML}^M . Thus, π -interaction is playing an important role for the lowering of Δ values in all the cases.

TABLE 1—MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF Zn²⁺ AND Cd²⁺ AT 30°
Ionic strength, 0.2M

Ligand (L)	$\log K_{Zn,L}^{Zn}$	$\log K_{Zn,2,2'bipy,L}^{Zn,2,2'bipy}$ (1:1:1)	$\log K_{Cd,L}^{Cd}$	$\log K_{Cd,2,2'bipy,L}^{Cd,2,2'bipy}$ (1:1:1)
Glycine	5.22	4.81 \pm 0.06	4.24	4.20 \pm 0.04
α -Alanine	5.17	4.54 \pm 0.04	4.27	4.05 \pm 0.02
Leucine	4.74	4.48 \pm 0.05	3.92	3.93 \pm 0.04
Valine	4.74	4.69 \pm 0.06	3.91	3.81 \pm 0.04
Serine	5.06	4.79 \pm 0.03	3.95	3.76 \pm 0.05
Threonine	5.16	4.89 \pm 0.06	4.02	3.86 \pm 0.02
Methionine	4.69	4.59 \pm 0.04	4.30	3.89 \pm 0.03

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